

TYPES OF POLYSEMY AND THEIR COGNITIVE-SEMANTIC ASPECTS

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Abstract. It is generally known that most words convey several concepts and thus possess the corresponding number of meanings. A word having several meanings is called polysemantic, and the ability of words to have more than one meaning is described by the term polysemy. This article describes some types of polysemy and their cognitive-semantic aspects.

Key words: types polysemy, regular polysemy, inherent polysemy, irregular polysemy.

Polysemy is characterized as the phenomenon whereby a single word form is associated with two or several related senses. It is distinguished from *monosemy*, where one word form is associated with a single meaning, and *homonymy*, where a single word form is associated with two or several unrelated meanings. Although the distinctions between polysemy, monosemy, and homonymy may seem clear at an intuitive level, they have proven difficult to draw in practice. Polysemy proliferates in natural language: Virtually every word is polysemous to some extent. Still, the phenomenon has been largely ignored in the mainstream linguistics literature and in related disciplines such as philosophy of language. However, polysemy is a topic of relevance to linguistic and philosophical debates regarding lexical meaning representation, compositional semantics, and the semantics-pragmatics divide. Early accounts treated polysemy in terms of sense enumeration: each sense of a polysemous expression is represented individually in the lexicon, such that polysemy and homonymy were treated on a pair. This approach has been strongly criticized on both theoretical and empirical grounds.

Polysemy is characterized as the phenomenon whereby a single word form is associated with two or several *related* senses, as in below:

John has his *mouth* full of food

Mary kissed him on the *mouth*

My *mouth* is sore

The *mouth* of the wine was dry

I have three *mouths* to feed

You can see the *mouth* of the river from here

The relations between the senses are often metonymic. Polysemy is contrasted with monosemy, on the one hand, and with homonymy, on the other. While a monosemous word form has only one meaning, a homonymous word form is associated with two or several *unrelated* meanings (e.g., *coach*: ‘bus’, ‘sports instructor’), and is standardly viewed as involving different lexemes.

According to Apresjan, regular polysemy is typically associated with senses generated by metonymical relations and irregular polysemy with senses that are derived metaphorically. Metaphor and metonymy are pragmatic processes that may target individual lexical items, and their role in the generation of polysemy has long been recognized. While metaphor is taken to involve a similarity relation between two entities (e.g., ‘Jane is (like a) princess’), metonymy is seen as involving real-world contiguity relations (e.g., ‘The ham sandwich left without paying’). These associations are based on the observation that many systematic sense alternations (e.g., ‘fruit for tree’, ‘publication for publisher’, exhibited by words such as *cherry*, *apple*, *New York Times*, etc.) seem to involve metonymic relations between senses. They are clearly different from creative metaphors, which are usually one-off and, if conventionalized, would typically be instances of irregular polysemy in Apresjan’s sense. They are also different from “everyday” metaphors (e.g., “Bill is a *bulldozer*”, “The critics *slaughtered* his new book”), which, although often conventional, cannot be said to involve any kind of regularity in the above sense. However, there are numerous cases of creative metonymy that are not obviously

regular either (e.g., “Jane is just *a pretty face*”, “*The loudmouth* is coming to the party”, “John has married *a free ticket to the opera*”, etc.). And there are instances of metaphor which appear to be at least partly regular, such as metaphorical uses of animal-denoting nouns to refer to some human characteristic (e.g., “Peter is *a lion/chicken/pig*”) or uses of body parts to refer to analogous parts of inanimate objects (e.g., *foot* of a mountain/tree/table, *mouth* of a bottle/river/cave). In other words, the association between regular polysemy and metonymy on the one hand, and irregular polysemy and metaphor on the other seems far from clear-cut.

Mary has written an excellent *book*

John sold his *books* to Mary

I have my *lunch* in the backpack

Lunch was really long today

Typically, inherent polysemy passes co-predication, anaphoric binding and conjunction reduction tests, as exemplified below:

The *book* has an interesting plot and an eye-catching cover

Lunch was delicious but took forever

Asher, in turn, distinguishes between *logical* and *accidental* polysemy, where logical polysemy is characterized as cases of polysemy that pass co-predication tests. Although co-predication tests are not completely reliable, they seem to reveal that we can think of objects that belong to different, complementary kinds, as coherent individual entities. At the same time, we can also conceptualize these objects as involving different entities. For instance, we can think about a book as a physical object only, as an informational entity only, or as both things at the same time. The idea is that such polysemous terms encode a new kind of type, a *dot object*, which is the result of merging two different types into a composite. So the noun *lunch* in “*Lunch* was delicious but took forever” is taken to be of the type.

REFERENCES

1. Cruse, D. A. *Meaning in Language. An Introduction to Semantics and Pragmatics.* University of Manchester: Oxford University Press. 2000.

2. Riemer, N. Cognitive Linguistics Research. The Semantics of Polysemy: Reading Meaning in English and Warlpiri. Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co. KG, D-10785, Germany: Berlin, 2005.
3. Irisqulov, M. T. Tilshunoslikka kirish. Second ed. Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2009.
4. Murphy, M.L. Lexical Meaning. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2010.
5. Lyons, J. Linguistic Semantics. UK: Cambridge University Press, 1995.
6. Lyons, J. Introduction to theoretical linguistics. UK: Cambridge University Press, 1968.